

Design, Optimization, And In-Vitro Evaluation Of A Tenueligliptin-Loaded Nanoemulsion Using Central Composite Design

Arijit Dutta¹, Debajit Dutta¹, Juti Rani Devi^{1*}, Manoj Kumar Deka², Bhargab Jyoti Sahariah²

¹ Department of pharmaceuticals, NETES Institute of Pharmaceutical Science, Nemcare Group of Institution, Mirza, Kamrup, Assam, India

² Department of pharmaceuticals, NETES Institute of Pharmaceutical Science, Nemcare Group of Institution, Mirza, Kamrup, Assam, India.

ABSTRACT

Tenueligliptin an anti-diabetic drug with low water solubility and dissolution-limited oral performance restricts its therapeutic effects in type 2 diabetes mellitus to some extent. The main aim of this study is to develop and optimize a nanoemulsion system to increase its solubility, stability, and release kinetics. A nanoemulsion was prepared using olive oil as the oil phase, Tween 80 as the primary emulsifier, and Span 20 as the co-surfactant. The droplet size was reduced and more uniform dispersion was obtained by ultrasonication. A Central Composite Design (CCD) was applied to assess how emulsifier and co-surfactant concentrations have effects on important formulation parameters, such as particle size, polydispersity index (PDI), and entrapment efficiency. ANOVA was used statically to validate the models that were produced after nine experimental runs. The optimized formulation F7 showed the particle size 8.65nm, PDI of 0.412 and zeta potential of -16.5mV with entrapment efficiency of 77.61% indicating stable formulation. FTIR analysis confirmed there is no chemical interactions between drug and excipients i.e., they are compatible with each other. Using a dialysis membrane setup *in-vitro* drug release was performed in phosphate buffer (pH 6.8), showing a sustained release of approx 74.89% over 40hrs. Release kinetics of the optimized formulation was set in mathematical models which demonstrating its Korsmeyer-Peppas model indicating complex diffusion controlled release behavior. Overall, Tenueligliptin physicochemical profile and release kinetics were significantly improved by an optimized nanoemulsion. These findings provide a strong support that nanoemulsion-based delivery has the great potential and an effective approach for enhancing the performance of poorly soluble drugs.

Keywords: Nanoemulsion, Tenueligliptin, sustained drug release, Central composite design

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes:

Diabetes mellitus is a long-term metabolic disorder indicated by increased blood sugar levels than normal, originates either the pancreas failed to produce sufficient insulin or the body's cells become ineffective or doesn't respond properly to it. Since insulin hormone is crucial for maintaining blood sugar levels and also facilitates the body to use glucose for energy, is either in insufficient production or not used

effectively. The primary types: type 1, type 2, and gestational diabetes (1).

Type 1 diabetes: This form of diabetes occurs when there is a situation of autoimmune attack where body unintentionally attacks and destroys its own pancreas's insulin-producing beta cells. As a result it leads to minimal or no insulin production. This type of patient requires lifelong insulin therapy and was frequently diagnosed in young people. (2).

Type 2 diabetes: It is the most common form, in this case the body develops resistance to insulin or the

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

pancreas can't produce enough insulin. Lifestyle factors like obesity, physical inactivity, and poor diet often plays a major role in its cause. With the increased rate of obesity among children and adolescents, type 2 diabetes diagnoses rate also becomes higher among them (3).

Gestational diabetes: This condition arises during pregnancy due to hormonal changes that involved in insulin action, creating risks to both mother and baby. Although it usually resolves during post pregnancy, it significantly increases the chance of type 2 diabetes in mother's later in life (4).

Frequent urination, excessive thirst, rapid weight loss, fatigue, blurred vision, and slow wound healing are the symptoms. Furthermore, some individuals with type 2 diabetes may lack symptoms at first, proving the significance of regular check-ups, especially for those with high risk factors such as obesity, family history, and sedentary lifestyles (5).

If keeps untreated it can have gradual effects on multiple organs and systems throughout the body, leads to several complications if not properly treated, which include the eyes to the kidneys, nerves, and cardiovascular system, diabetes may cause chaos on one's wee-being, causing in serious issues such as diabetic retinopathy, nephropathy, neuropathy, heart disease, stroke, peripheral artery disease, foot ulcers, infections, and even amputations [6].

Managing diabetes demands an integrated approach includes changes in lifestyle, medication, and careful monitoring of blood sugar levels. Lifestyle modification is essential for diabetes management, which includes maintaining a balanced diet, regular physical activity, weight management, and reduces the use of tobacco. These steps are essential for increasing the insulin sensitivity, promote the glucose uptake by cells, and reducing the risk of heart problems (7).

Teneligliptin:

Teneligliptin is an anti-diabetic drug treating type 2 diabetes mellitus, which belongs to the class of dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) inhibitors. Its pharmacological action shows by blocking the DPP-4 enzyme, thereby boosting the levels of incretin

hormones in the body primarily glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) and glucose-dependent insulinotropic polypeptide (GIP), which helps to control blood sugar levels by increasing insulin secretion and reducing glucagon release (8)

Usually teneligliptin taken once a day through orally, with or without food, as directed by healthcare practioner with prescribed dosage and proper instructions. Teneligliptin is generally well tolerated and can be effective in achieving better blood sugar levels when used alone or with combination with other antidiabetic agents. Common adverse effects include headache, upper respiratory tract infections, and nasopharyngitis (9)

Fig1: Structure of teneligliptin

It's mechanism involves by inhibiting of the enzyme dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4). Normally, DPP-4 breaks down incretin hormones such as glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) and glucose-dependent insulinotropic peptide (GIP). By inhibiting DPP-4, Teneligliptin prevents the breakdown of incretin hormones, resulting the prolong action of incretin hormones, resulting in increased insulin secretion and decreased glucagon secretion, thereby improving glucose control in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (10). Clinical studies have shown that Teneligliptin lowers HbA1c levels, and also poses minimal risk of hypoglycemia. Additional some evidences also suggest cardiovascular and renal protective effect in diabetic patients (11).

However Teneligliptin exhibits low aqueous solubility and dissolution-limited oral performance, which restricts pharmacological action. To enhance its solubility and absorption efficiency, an optimized formulation strategy is required

Nano-emulsion:

Lipid-based formulations have become a major approach for boosting the oral in-vitro performance of drugs that don't dissolve well in water. When lipophilic drugs are incorporated into oils, surfactants, or other lipid carriers, their solubility and membrane permeability improve noticeably. (11). Nanoemulsions have gained a lot interest in the fields of nanotechnology and colloid science. They consist of tiny droplets of one liquid dispersed in another immiscible liquid—typically for oil and water—which is stabilized by surfactants that avoid the droplets from getting fusing together. Generally the droplets typically fall in the 20–200 nm range (12). However sometimes surfactant rich nanoemulsions systems have droplet size less than 20 nm indicating mixed colloidal dispersion, effective for solubilization of low aqueous soluble of drugs.

Their tiny size results in high surface area, which improves drug solubility and absorption. (13). The nanoemulsions can be produced through high energy techniques and low energy techniques, each offering its own advantages and challenges. High-energy methods such as high-pressure homogenization, ultrasonication, and microfluidization, and low-energy methods like phase inversion and spontaneous emulsification, are commonly used. The optimal method depends on desired droplet size, formulation requirements, and scalability. Each method presents unique chances for customizing nanoemulsions for specific applications and maximizes their effectiveness (14).

This drug delivery system enhances the dissolution rate, in-vitro performance and also bypassing first-pass metabolism making it effective for Biopharmaceutics Classification System (BCS) class II and IV drugs. (15-17).

So to the given poor solubility and low oral in-vitro performance of Teneligliptin, formulating it as a nano-emulsion offers us to overcome limitations like dissolution stability, intestinal permeability increasing its therapeutic efficacy. So the present study is to develop the teneligliptin nano emulsion for improved stability, solubility and in-vitro performance resulting enhancing its therapeutic efficacy in management of type 2 diabetes mellitus.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**2.1 MATERIALS, INSTRUMENTS AND APPARATUS USED****2.1.1. MATERIALS:**

The materials which we are using are mentioned below. All the materials have been used were of reagent grade.

Teneligliptin

Tween-80

Span-20

Distilled water

Sodium Lauryl Sulphate

Olive oil

Dialysis membrane

Membrane filter (0.45 micrometer)

2.1.2 .INSTRUMENTS USED:

Zeta-sizer (Melvern)

Probe-sonicator (Labman Scientific Instruments)

UV-Spectrophotometer (Shimadzu)

Measuring balance (Saffron)

Magnetic stirrer and hot plate (neuation)

FTIR-Spectrophotometer (Bruker)

Micro-pipette

Ultracentrifuge

g) Dissolution Apparatus (Lab India)

2.1.3 APPARATUS USED:

Measuring cylinder (Borosil)

Beakers (Borosil)

Pipettes

Glassrods

Test tubes(Borosil,10ml)

Crystallizing plate (Borosil)

2.2 METHODS

2.2.1. PREFORMULATION STUDIES

A. PHYSICAL OBSERVATION:

The colour and powder forms of the drug teneligliptin was observed and identified as per the standard.

B. MELTING POINT:

The melting point of Teneligliptin was determined by melting point apparatus and found to comply with the melting point of reference sample.

C. SOLUBILITY:

The solubility of Teneligliptin was observed in different solvents such as water, ethanol, acetone at room temperature.

D. SPECTRAL ANALYSIS AND VALIDATION OF SPECTROSCOPIC METHOD:

The UV-Vis spectrophotometric analytical method for quantifying teneligliptin was developed and validated according to International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines. This validation will assess in respect to linearity, detection limit, quantification limit, accuracy and precision.(18)

To determine analytical wavelength, 10 µg/ml concentration of Teneligliptin was prepared in ethanol which will be scanned against ethanol as blank and the wavelength at which maximum absorbance occurs will be recorded.

For sample preparation, precisely weighed 1 mg of standard Teneligliptin will be dissolved in 10 ml of ethanol to create a standard stock solution. From this standard stock solution, the series of dilutions will be made to obtain concentration ranging in between 2-10 µg/ml using ethanol. These diluted solutions will be analysed for linearity will be determined at concentration levels ranging between 2-10 µg/ml.(19)

E.DRUG-EXCIPIENT COMPATIBILITY STUDIES: INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY

Spectra were recorded in the wave number range 400-4000 cm⁻¹ with a resolution of 4cm⁻¹. Each spectrum represents an average of 32 scans. FTIR study will be performed for Teneligliptin, excipients and prepared excipients compatibility study will be performed by using FTIR Spectroscopy.(20)

2.2.2 FORMULATION STUDIES:

A. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN:

Teneligliptin loaded nanoemulsion was optimized using central composite design in design expert software. This statistical design consists of total 9 experimental runs, each carried in fully randomized manner. The concentration of emulsifier (X1) and surfactant concentration (X2) were selected as independent variables while PDI and particle size were selected as dependent variables. Statistical significance was determined by P-value which was less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. With all parameters kept constant, selected variables (Y1) and (Y2) were assess at different levels such as low (0.5) and high (2). Response surface methodology was applied to generate model graphs which were then used to analyzed the observed response. (21)

Table 1: list of dependent and independent variables

3. PREPARATION OF TENELIGLIPTIN NANO-EMULSION:

Independent variable	Variable level	
	Low(-1)	High (+1)
Amount of Emulsifier(X1)	0.5 ml	2ml
Amount of surfactant(X2)	0.5 ml	2 ml
Dependent variable		
Y1= Particle Size		
Y2= PDI		

To prepare a nano emulsion, firstly the aqueous phase was prepared by mixing water with surfactants like Sodium Lauryl Sulfate (SLS), along with emulsifier like Tween 80, and a co-emulsifier ie, Span 20. These components facilitate emulsification by lowering interfacial tension between the water and oil phases. Simultaneously, the oil phase is prepared separately

which often containing oils like Olive oil. Once both phases are prepared, under high-speed stirring the oil phase is slowly gradually added to the aqueous phase. This ensures appropriate dispersion and prevents large droplet formation. Then the mixture is subjected to sonicate via probe sonicator. Sonication breaks down larger droplets into smaller droplets also helps in proper mixing if it.

Table 2: formulation and production condition

Formulation code	Tween80 (X1)mg	Span20 (X2) ml	Drug mg
F1	1.25	2	10
F2	0.5	0.5	10
F3	2	1.25	10
F4	0.5	2	10
F5	2	0.5	10
F6	1.25	1.25	10
F7	0.5	1.25	10
F8	1.25	0.5	10
F9	2	2	10

4. EVALUATION OF NANO EMULSION:

A. PARTICLE SIZE, POLYDISPERSITY INDEX AND ZETA POTENTIAL ANALYSIS:

The average particle size, size distribution (polydispersity index, PDI) and zeta potential of the

nano emulsions were assessed by using the dynamic light scattering method with Zeta- Sizer (Melvern). The nano emulsions were diluted with distilled water to appropriate concentrations to obtain better focusing positions and attenuation. (22)

B. DRUG ENTRAPMENT EFFICIENCY (%) AND DRUG LOADING DETERMINATION:

To determine the %EE of nano emulsion, samples were put in the High-Speed Centrifugation at 14500 rpm for 30 min. The resultant supernatant was appropriately diluted and analyzed spectrophotometer at λ_{max} , 243 nm to measure the amount of drug presents (39). The experiment was performed in triplicate and the %EE was calculated using the following equation:

$$EE\% = \frac{\text{Weight of total drug} - \text{weight of free drug}}{\text{Weight of total drug}} \times 100$$

C. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed on the experimental data, with statistical significance $p < 0.05$). The statistical analysis was carried out using design expert software (StateEase, Inc. Minneapolis. (23)

D. OPTIMIZATION AND VALIDATION OF OPTIMIZED CONDITION:

A central composite design was used to optimize the formulation of nano particles. The amounts of emulsifier i.e. Tween 80 (X1) and amount of surfactant i.e. span 20 (X2) were chosen as independent variables. X1 and X2 are coded levels of independent variables. X1 and X2 represents the interaction term. The main effects (X1 and X2) indicate the average impact of changing one factor at a time from its low to high value. The interaction terms shows how the response changes when both factors are changed simultaneously. For every sample two responses, Particle Size (Y1) and entrapment efficiency EE (Y2) were measured and taken as dependent variables. (24)

E. IN-VITRO DRUG RELEASE STUDY OF OPTIMIZED FORMULATION:

In-vitro release of Tenueligliptin from nanoemulsion was performed by using dialysis membrane method with fully calibrated eight station USP type-II dissolution test apparatus with phosphate buffer of pH 6.8 (11.45g Potassium di-hydrogen phosphate, 13.80g disodium hydrogen phosphate), at $35 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The nanoemulsion was loaded in the dialysis membrane (14000 Dalton MWCO, Sigma) with the openings sealed and then suspended in 900ml phosphate buffer

at $35 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ with agitation speed of 50rpm. At specific intervals, 5ml samples were withdrawn and replaced with fresh buffer at the same temperature was added to maintain the constant conditions. All samples were analyzed by using UV-Visible Spectrophotometer at a maximum wavelength of 243 nm. (25)

F. DRUG RELEASE KINETICS STUDY OF OPTIMIZED FORMULATION:

The release pattern of tenueligliptin from nanoemulsion was evaluated by fitting the dissolution data to multiple kinetic models including zero-order release kinetics, first-order release kinetics, and Higuchi model. Additional release parameters were calculated from the release data. To further evaluate the mechanism of drug release Korsmeyer-Peppas's equation was applied enabling the determination of release exponent " n " and " k " the release rate constant, and " R " the regression coefficient providing the underlying release behaviour. (22)

i. Zero order kinetics:

For Zero order kinetics the graph of cumulative % drug release against time will be linear. The zero-order model is mathematically represented by the following equation:

$$Q_t = Q_0 + K_0 t$$

Where, Q_t = the amount of drug release in time t

Q_0 = the initial amount of drug in the solution K_0 = the zero order release rate

ii. First order kinetics:

In first order kinetics the graph of log cumulative % drug retained versus time will be linear and the slope will give the value of K . The following equation is used to express the first order model,

$$\text{Log} Q_t = \text{Log} Q_0 + K_1 t / 2.303$$

Where, Q_t = the amount of drug release in time t

Q_0 = the initial amount of drug in the solution

K_1 = the first order release rate constant

iii. Higuchi model:

In Higuchi model the graph is cumulative % drug release versus square root of time. The following equation is used to express the Higuchi model,

$$Q = [D (2C - C_s) C_s t]^{1/2}$$

Where, Q = the amount of drug released in time t C = the total drug concentration

C_s = the drug soluble in matrix

D = the diffusion constant of the drug in the matrix

The equation of Higuchi has been further modified to the following expression (generally known as simplified Higuchi model)

$$Q = K_h t^{1/2}$$

Where, K_h = the Higuchi dissolution rate constant

iv. Korsemyer-Peppas model:

In Korsemyer-Peppas

the graph is log cumulative versus log time. This model is expressed by the following,

$$M_t/M_\infty = K t^n$$

Where, M_t/M_∞ = the fraction of drug released at time t

K = the rate constant

n = the release exponent

t = release time

For the determination of exponent 'n' the region of their release curve where,

$M_t/M_\infty < 0.6$ should be used.

Peppas in 1985 developed this 'n' value to characterize different release mechanisms as shown in the following table. This model is applicable to assess the release profile of pharmaceutical dosage forms, whether the release mechanism is well known or when multiple release phenomena may be present same time

Table 3: Rate and mechanism of release corresponding to different n values according to Korsemyer-Peppas model

Release exponent 'n'	Drug transport Mechanism	Rate as a function of time
≤0.5	Fickian diffusion	t ^{-0.5}
0.5 < n < 1.0	Non-Fickian diffusion	t ⁿ⁻¹
1.0	Case II transport	Zero order release
Higher than 1.0	Supercase II transport	t ⁿ⁻¹

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**A. PHYSICAL OBSERVATION:****a. PREFORMULATION STUDY**

Table 4: Physical observation

Parameter	Observation
Colour	White
Appearance	Powder form

B. MELTINGPOINT:

The melting point of Teneligliptin was found to be $217 \pm 0.9^\circ\text{C}$

C. SOLUBILITY:**Table 5: Solubility**

Solvent	Solubility
Water	Poorly soluble in intestinal pH
Ethanol	Soluble
Acetone	Soluble

D. SPECTRAL ANALYSIS AND VALIDATION OF SPECTROSCOPIC METHOD:

The analytical wavelength of Teneligliptin was found to be 243nm.

FTIR analysis was done to authenticate the stability. The figure shows the spectra of olive oil, Sodium Lauryl Sulphate, Span20, Tween80, teneligliptin, physical mixture. The spectra Teneligliptin shows band at 3396.99 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of the amino group. The peak at 2922.39 cm^{-1} and 2853.32 are attributed to the groups -C-H- stretching and -O=H stretching while another peak at 1738.92 cm^{-1} belongs to the (C=O) ester fatty acid. The band at 1563.31 cm^{-1} shows C=C stretching, 1463.26 cm^{-1} shows C=H bending and 1416.42 cm^{-1} show O-H bending, 1377.13 cm^{-1} shows C-H aliphatic, 1231.93 cm^{-1} shows C-N amide, 1169.18 cm^{-1} belong to -O-H groups. The enol C-O stretching peak was observed at 1069.53 cm^{-1} . 872.71 cm^{-1} peak shows C=O bending. 773.36 cm^{-1} peak shows C-H bending. 721.64 cm^{-1} peak shows benzene derivatives and 656.52 cm^{-1} peak shows C-H aromatic.

The FTIR spectrum for the physical mixture shows functional group peaks of teneligliptin which are responsible for its structural activity. So, it can be concluded that there is no physical or chemical interaction between the drug and the excipients.

b. FORMULATION OF THENANO-EMULSION:

A. PREPARATION OF TENELIGLIPTIN LOADED NANOEMULSION:

The preparation of teneligliptin loaded nano emulsion was done by above mentioned method. The Central Composite Design gives us 9 formulation variations in the independent factors.

Figure 4: Prepared Teneligliptin loaded nanoemulsion

c. EVALUATIONS OF THE NANOEMULSION:

A. PARTICLE SIZE, POLYDISPERSITY INDEX(PDI) AND ZETA POTENTIAL:

The particle size, PDI and zeta potential of teneligliptin loaded nano emulsion were determined by using zeta sizer. The parameters were measured by using redispersed pellets of teneligliptin nanoemulsion.

The particle sizes of all the formulation were found to be in the range of 8.65 nm to 38.74 nm , following that

the PDI of the formulations were found to be between 0.412 to

0.208 and zeta potential were found to be between -28.4 mV to -16.5 mV . The exceptionally small droplets is being observed may indicate the formation of surfactant-rich nanoemulsion domains or mixed micellar-nanoemulsion systems.

Table 6: Particle size, Zeta potential and PDI

RUN	PARTICLESIZE (nm)	ZETA POTENTIAL	PDI
F1	10.686	-17.3	0.208
F2	16.931	-19.5	0.407
F3	17.42	-23.1	0.341
F4	15.433	-20.7	0.327
F5	38.74	-27	0.355
F6	11.453	-25.7	0.312
F7	8.65	-16.5	0.412
F8	21.4	-28.4	0.346
F9	13.84	-22.5	0.248

B. DRUG ENTRAPMENT EFFICIENCY (%EE) DETERMINATION:

The % entrapment efficiency of the prepared formulations were found to be as following;

The % entrapment efficiency of the formulation was determined using the previously mentioned formula.

Table7: Entrapment Efficiency

Formulation code	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
%EE	78.15	81.29	79.92	83.65	87.55	84.12	77.61	89.49	85.69

C. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied to the experimental data, considering the results associated

with significance level. The design expert software (State-Ease, Inc. Minneapolis). was used for the statistical analysis.

Run	Factor 1 A: tween 80 ml	Factor 2 B: Span 20 ml	Response 1 particle size nm	Response 2 PDI
1	1.25	2	10.686	0.208
2	0.5	0.5	16.931	0.407
3	2	1.25	17.42	0.341
4	0.5	2	15.433	0.327
5	2	0.5	38.74	0.355
6	1.25	1.25	11.453	0.312
7	0.5	1.25	8.65	0.412
8	1.25	0.5	21.4	0.346
9	2	2	13.84	0.248

Table8: Experimental design runs

Build Information

File Version	13.0.5.0		
Study Type	Response Surface	Subtype	Randomized
Design Type	Central Composite	Runs	9.00
Design Model	Quadratic	Blocks	No Blocks
Build Time(ms)	2.00		

For statistical analysis design expert version 13.0.5.0 using Response surface and the data were fitted into Central composite design in which various model i.e.,

Linear, 2FI, Quadratic and Cubic analyzed. Amongst that Quadratic model displays the best results.

Model Summary Statistics**Response 1: Particle size**

Source	Sequential p-value	Adjusted R ²	Predicted R ²	
Linear	0.0777	0.4310	-0.2033	
2FI	0.0766	0.6570	-0.2909	
Quadratic	0.0151	0.9650	0.8829	Suggested
Cubic	0.8281	0.9281	-0.6383	Aliased

The Predicted R² of 0.8829 is in reasonable agreement with the Adjusted R² of 0.9650; i.e. the difference is less than 0.2.

Response 2: PDI

Source	Sequential p-value	Lack of Fit p-value	Adjusted R ²	Predicted R ²	
Linear	0.0310		0.5814	0.3829	
2FI	0.7849		0.5058	0.3243	
Quadratic	0.0159		0.9480	0.7654	Suggested
Cubic	0.1835		0.9947	0.8803	Aliased

The Predicted R² of 0.7654 is in reasonable agreement with the Adjusted R² of 0.9480; i.e. the difference is less than 0.2.

Response no.	P-value	F-value
Response1 (Particle Size)	0.0050	45.18
Response2 (PDI)	0.0091	30.18

Response 1, The Model F-value of 45.18 implies the model is significant. There is only a 0.50% chance that an F-value this large could occur due to noise. P-values less than 0.0500 indicate model terms are significant.

Response 2 The Model F-value of 30.18 implies the model is significant. There is only a 0.91% chance that an F-value this large could occur due to noise.

P- Values less than 0.0500 indicate model terms are significant.

D. OPTIMIZATION AND VALIDATION OF THE OPTIMIZED FORMULATION:

In this study the linear model provided us the optimal condition to prepare the formulation as desirability

serves as the purpose to decide on picking an appropriate combination of formulation. The quadratic model shows F7 as appropriate formulation combination with desirability close to 1.

Fig 5: Response Surface plot for Particle Size

Fig 6: Response Surface plot for PDI

Fig 7: Actual vs Predicted plot for Particle Size

Fig 8: Actual vs Predicted plot for PDI

Fig 9: Contour plot for Particle Size

Fig 10: Contour plot for PDI

100 Solutions found

Number	tween80	Span 20	particlesize	PDI	Desirability	
4	0.500	1.250	9.006	0.409	1.000	Selected

The numerical statistics generates 100 solutions with different combination of independent variable. Out of 100 solutions 8 solution fall under the formulation design. Among the 8 solution number 4 solution was

selected having combination of independent variable “- 1,0 ”which represents formulation F7, due to the less deviation in predicted and the actual values.

Fig 11: Particle size and PDI of the optimized formulation

Fig12: Zeta potential of the optimized formulation

E. IN-VITRO DRUG RELEASE:**Fig13: Results of drug release****Table9: Results of Dissolution study**

Time	Cum% drug release
0	0
0.5	2.04477612
1	4.910447762
2	8.253731344
4	12.49253731
6	17.28358209
8	22.68656716
10	27.68656716
12	34.89552239
14	41.70149254
18	48.88059702
24	56.80597015
36	65.62686567
40	74.895522239

F. IN-VITRO DRUG RELEASE KINETICS:

The drug release pattern of teneligliptin loaded nano emulsion was analyzed by several kinetic models, including Zero-Order, First-Order, Korsmeyer Peppas, Higuchi models. For each model, the release constant and regression co-efficient (R²) was calculated from the slopes of appropriate plots

allowing comparison of the release kinetics and model fit.

Table10: Kinetic Model Parameters

Kinetic Model	F7
Zero order	$y=1.8517x -6.7164$ $R^2=0.9867$ $K=1.8517$
First order	$Y=-0.0142x+1.9923$ $R^2=0.9448$ $K=-0.0142$
Higuchi	$Y=12.595x-8.0661$ $R^2=0.9746$ $K=12.595$
Korsemeyer-Peppas	$Y=1.6081x+0.6364$ $R^2=0.9896$ $n=1.6081$ $K=0.6364$

From the R2 value it can be concluded that the teneligliptin loaded nano emulsion formulation follows the Zero order of drug release, it describes the drug release from the formulation is independent of concentration. For explaining the mechanism of drug release from teneligliptin loaded nano emulsion,

Korsemeyer Peppas equation showed good linearity and the release exponent $n > 1$ demonstrating complex release behavior. Since the formulation doesn't contain any swellable polymer matrix, the reason behind this due to interfacial diffusion and surfactant layer reorganization.

Fig 16: Release plot in Higushi model

Fig 17: Release plot in Korsmeyer's-Peppasmodel

6. DISCUSSION:

The Teneligliptin-loaded nanoemulsion was successfully formulated using Tween 80 as the surfactant alongside Span 20 as the co-surfactant, with the goal of enhancing the drug's solubility, stability, and controlled release. RSM in combination with Central Composite Design (CCD) was used to optimize the formulation parameters. Tween 80 and Span 20 were taken as the independent variables because of their important role in lowering the interfacial tension, droplets stabilization and also influencing the overall droplet size distribution.

Particle Size, PDI, and Zeta Potential

All formulations produced droplet sizes ranging from 8.65 nm to 38.74 nm, demonstrating the successful formation of nanoemulsions. Among them formulation (F7) showed the smallest droplet size of 8.65 nm, demonstrating a high stable nanoscale dispersion that helps in drug solubilization and absorption. The PDI values ranged from 0.208 to 0.412, indicating a uniform size distribution among the formulations; particularly F7, with a PDI of 0.412, maintain within the acceptable range for nanoemulsions (<0.5). The zeta potential values ranged from -16.5 mV to -28.4 mV, indicating that droplet aggregation is avoided by moderate electrostatic repulsion. While larger absolute zeta potential values generally signify better stability, the combined effects of surfactant stabilization and the

nanoscale size provided acceptable colloidal stability for all formulations.

Entrapment Efficiency (%EE)

Entrapment efficiencies ranged from 77.61% to 89.49%. The optimized formulation F7 recorded an EE of 77.61%, demonstrating effective drug encapsulation within the oil-surfactant interface. The slightly lower %EE in F7 is observed compared to others as rest formulations have bigger size or high PDI it is reasonable as it can be driven by increased drug distribution into aqueous phase at higher surfactant level combining with smaller droplet sizes is expected leads to increase in exposure at interfacial region. However, the level of entrapment was sufficient for controlled and sustained drug delivery.

Statistical Optimization and Model Analysis

ANOVA and regression analysis demonstrated that the quadratic model was appropriate for the experimental data for both particle size and PDI, as reflected by high Adjusted R^2 and Predicted R^2 values (0.9650 and 0.8829 for particle size; 0.9480 and 0.7654 for PDI). The F-values (45.18 for particle size and 30.18 for PDI) with $p < 0.05$ indicating that the models were significant effect, confirming the influence of Tween 80 and Span 20 concentrations on droplet size and distribution. The optimization process identified F7 (Tween 80 = 0.5 mL, Span 20 = 1.25 mL) as the optimal formulation, closely matched predicted desirability of 1.000. The experimental outcomes closely aligned with the predicted values, supporting the design model's reliability.

In-Vitro Drug Release and Kinetics

The in-vitro dissolution release showed a sustained release of 74.89% of Teneligliptin over a period of 40 hours. The initial slow-release phase (0–8 h) is likely reflects the diffusion through the surfactant interface, which is followed by a controlled release phase caused by the gradual diffusion of the drug from the internal oil core into the aqueous environment. Although the release data showed good linearity with the zero-order model ($R^2 = 0.9867$), a better fit was observed with the Korsmeyer–Peppas model, indicating that the release mechanism is likely governed by complex interfacial dynamics rather than

purely zero-order kinetics. Further mechanistic evaluation using the Korsmeyer–Peppas model ($R^2 = 0.9896$, $n = 1.6081$) demonstrates that the drug release from the nanoemulsion matrix is largely governed by the structural relaxation of the interfacial layer combined with ongoing diffusion through the surfactant film.

Overall Interpretation

The collected data demonstrate that the optimized Teneligliptin nanoemulsion (F7) has significant properties that increases in-vitro performance and improved extended drug release. The nanoscale droplet size made it guaranteed that increased surface area for absorption, while the controlled release profile supports sustained therapeutic levels. The validation of the model and desirability evaluation reaffirm that CCD is an efficient approach for systematically optimizing nanoemulsion formulations.

7. CONCLUSION:

The Teneligliptin nano emulsions were prepared by emulsification method with modification by simultaneously using ultrasonication. Where Tween 80 was used as a emulsifier of choice and Sodium Lauryl Sulphate as the surfactant. Central composite design was used to design various formulation runs while Response Surface methodology (RSM) was used to statistically optimize a formulation. In-vitro dissolution study provides us with the confirmation that the formulations do follow a control release pattern. Teneligliptin loaded nano emulsion were prepared with an objective to overcome the problem associated with absorption of teneligliptin. The statistical analysis shows the formulation F7 with a high desirability which is close to 1 with particle size 8.65 nm, narrow PDI, moderate electrostatic stabilization zeta potential and sufficient %entrapment efficiency of 77.61 against independent variable condition of amount of emulsifier i.e. 0.5ml and surfactant 1.25ml. The optimized formulation supports the potential of surfactant rich nanoemulsion system for dissolution limited anti-diabetic drugs, required in-vivo evaluation.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest

FUNDING

Self-funded

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I acknowledge to the Department of Pharmaceutics, Nemcare group of institution.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Arijit Dutta and Juti Rani Devi design and analyzed the research, Arijit Dutta perform the research work, Debajit Dutta wrote the manuscript, Manoj Kumar Deka and Bhargab Jyoti Sahariah supervised manuscript.

REFERENCES

1. Singh R, Gholipourmalekabadi M, Shafikhani SH. Animal models for type 1 and type 2 diabetes: advantages and limitations. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne)*. 2024;15:1359685.
2. Desai T, Shea LD. Advances in islet encapsulation technologies. *Nat Rev Drug Discov*. 2017 May;16(5):338–50.
3. Yaribeygi H, Maleki M, Sathyapalan T, Jamialahmadi T, Sahebkar A. Obesity and Insulin Resistance: A Review of Molecular Interactions. *Curr Mol Med*. 2021;21(3):182–93.
4. Healy AM. Diabetes in Pregnancy: Preconception to Postpartum. *Prim Care*. 2022 Jun;49(2):287–300.
5. Dmello MM, Bhagwat G. Novel Approaches to Control Diabetes. *Curr Diabetes Rev*. 2024;20(5):e090823219599.
6. Alotaibi A, Alqhtani N, Alluhaymid A, Alhomaidan L, Alwabel M, Algurafi A, et al. Awareness of Diabetic Patients in the Qassim Region About Diabetic Foot and Its Complications. *Cureus*. 2024 Jan;16(1):e52306.
7. Pascual Fuster V, Pérez Pérez A, Carretero Gómez J, Caixàs Pedragós A, Gómez-Huelgas R, Pérez-Martínez P. Executive summary: Updates to the dietary treatment of prediabetes and type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Rev Clin Esp*. 2021 Mar;221(3):169–79.
8. Tsuchimochi W, Ueno H, Yamashita E, Tsubouchi C, Sakoda H, Nakamura S, et al. Tenueligliptin improves glycemic control with the reduction of postprandial insulin requirement in Japanese diabetic patients. *Endocr J*. 2015;62(1):13–20.
9. Panikar V, Joshi S, Tiwaskar M, Bhondve A, Nasikkar N, Walawalkar S, et al. Study of the Efficacy of Uptitrating Tenueligliptin Dose from Standard Dose (20 mg) to High Dose (40 mg) in Patients with Type II Diabetes Mellitus. *J Assoc Physicians India*. 2022 Jul;70(7):11–2.
10. Ceriello A, De Nigris V, Iijima H, Matsui T, Gouda M. The Unique Pharmacological and Pharmacokinetic Profile of Tenueligliptin: Implications for Clinical Practice. *Drugs*. 2019 May;79(7):733–50.
11. Silberstein S, Spierings ELH, Kunkel T. Celecoxib Oral Solution and the Benefits of Self-Microemulsifying Drug Delivery Systems (SMEDDS) Technology: A Narrative Review. *Pain Ther*. 2023 Oct;12(5):1109–19.
12. Ozogul Y, Karsli GT, Durmuş M, Yazgan H, Oztop HM, McClements DJ, et al. Recent developments in industrial applications of nanoemulsions. *Adv Colloid Interface Sci*. 2022 Jun;304:102685.
13. Salvia-Trujillo L, Soliva-Fortuny R, Rojas-Graü MA, McClements DJ, Martín-Belloso O. Edible Nanoemulsions as Carriers of Active Ingredients: A Review. *Annu Rev Food Sci Technol*. 2017 Feb;8:439–66.
14. Kumar M, Bishnoi RS, Shukla AK, Jain CP. Techniques for Formulation of Nanoemulsion Drug Delivery System: A Review. *Prev Nutr food Sci*. 2019 Sep;24(3):225–34.
15. Lu WC, Huang DW, Wang CCR, Yeh CH, Tsai JC, Huang YT, et al. Preparation, characterization, and antimicrobial activity of nanoemulsions incorporating citral essential oil. *J food drug Anal*. 2018 Jan;26(1):82–9.
16. Li SJ, Liao YF, Du Q. [Research and application of quercetin-loaded nano drug delivery system]. *Zhongguo Zhong yao za zhi = Zhongguo zhongyao zazhi = China J Chinese Mater medica*. 2018 May;43(10):1978–84.

17. Bhalani D V, Nutan B, Kumar A, Singh Chandel AK. In-vitro performance Enhancement Techniques for Poorly Aqueous Soluble Drugs and Therapeutics. *Biomedicines*. 2022 Aug;10(9).
18. Kadukkattil Ramanunni A, Singh SK, Wadhwa S, Gulati M, Kapoor B, Khursheed R, et al. Overcoming hydrolytic degradation challenges in topical delivery: non-aqueous nano-emulsions. *Expert Opin Drug Deliv*. 2022 Jan;19(1):23–45.
19. Zaafar D, Khalil HMA, Elkhoully GE, Sedeky AS, Ahmed YH, Khalil MG, et al. Preparation and characterization of Sorafenib nano-emulsion: impact on pharmacokinetics and toxicity; an in vitro and in vivo study. *Drug Deliv Transl Res*. 2024 Mar;
20. Patil J, Rajput R, Nemade R, Naik J. Preparation and characterization of artemether loaded solid lipid nanoparticles: a 32 factorial design approach. *Mater Technol*. 2020 Oct 14;35(11–12):719–26.
21. Sun J, Bi C, Chan HM, Sun S, Zhang Q, Zheng Y. Curcumin-loaded solid lipid nanoparticles have prolonged in vitro antitumour activity, cellular uptake and improved in vivo in-vitro performance. *Colloids Surfaces B Biointerfaces*. 2013 Nov 1;111:367–75.
22. Dara T, Vatanara A, Nabi Meybodi M, Vakilinezhad MA, Malvajerd SS, Vakhshiteh F, et al. Erythropoietin-loaded solid lipid nanoparticles: Preparation, optimization, and in vivo evaluation. *Colloids Surfaces B Biointerfaces*. 2019 Jun 1;178:307–16.
23. Arcari SG, Caliaro V, Sganzerla M, Godoy HT. Volatile composition of Merlot red wine and its contribution to the aroma: optimization and validation of analytical method. *Talanta* [Internet]. 2017;174:752–66. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2017.06.074>
24. Sabir F, Qindeel M, Rehman A ur, Ahmad NM, Khan GM, Csoka I, et al. An efficient approach for development and optimisation of curcumin-loaded solid lipid nanoparticles' patch for transdermal delivery. *J Microencapsul* [Internet]. 2021;38(4):233–48. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02652048.2021.1899321>
25. Khare A, Singh I, Pawar P, Grover K. Design and Evaluation of Voriconazole Loaded Solid Lipid Nanoparticles for Ophthalmic Application. *J Drug Deliv*. 2016 May 12;2016:1–11.

HOW TO CITE: Arijit Dutta, Debajit Dutta, Juti Rani Devi, Manoj Kumar Deka, Bhargab Jyoti Sahariah, Design, Optimization, And In-Vitro Evaluation Of A Teneligliptin-Loaded Nanoemulsion Using Central Composite Design, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (5), 716-735. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20478204>

